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A screen to identify genes that confer resistance to platinum chemotherapy.

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Resistance to chemotherapy remains an important clinical problem in medical oncology. Identifying precise molecular mechanisms by which the tumor amounts a resistance response remains a high priority scientific goal. We integrated whole transcriptome data generated using RNA-sequencing, studying multiple in vitro cellular models of resistance to platinum chemotherapy in cancer cells to identify genes of interest functioning in platinum resistance. The collection of genes identified in these expression screens as likely to be important or functional relevant for mechanisms governing platinum resistance included the E3 ubiquitin ligase enzymes TRIM35 and TRIM21.